

ANALYSIS OF THE PROBLEM OF USING DIDACTIC GAMES IN STUDENT EDUCATION AND TEACHING

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Abstract. *The use of didactic games in the process of education and training of students is important today. Therefore, the content of this article was focused on the analysis of the problem of using didactic games in educating and teaching students.*

Keywords: *education of students, didactic games, child, school, learning, mastering, educational activities.*

The child comes to school with great enthusiasm. How to keep this feeling of joyful surprise for a long time before school, before the secrets that await him there? How to chain his unstable attention without forcing him to study? What tools and methods should be used to make learning interesting? —, in order to search for and answer questions that are correct and accurate in content, the following opinions were presented.

Unfortunately, in recent years, more and more children come to school, characterized by a low level of school maturity, who experience difficulties in learning and mastering the social role of a student from the first days, and the risk of adaptation at school increases. When working with children, the teacher should first of all aim to create conditions for the comprehensive development of each child, to expand his opportunities and to acquire knowledge, not the traditional task of imparting knowledge. An underdeveloped field of self-discipline does not allow children to fully perform regular and intensive educational activities. On the contrary, it causes children to get tired quickly.

Is there a solution for this or where is the solution? It is natural that the question arises. The answer is simple - the solution lies on the surface. Any person is happy to do what he is interested in. Including a child, that is, a child plays with interest. Therefore, the game should be used as the most important tool for the activation of the child's cognitive abilities and its development.

It's no secret that people should learn their mother tongue from early childhood, but special attention should be paid to it in primary education processes. The knowledge of the native language acquired by students in primary grades is the key to the real development of knowledge, education and consciousness, it ensures the formation of a materialistic worldview, the development of abstract thinking and provides theoretical knowledge. It also serves as a basis for acquiring spelling, grammatical, orthographic skills and qualifications. All this is important in improving the quality of knowledge and literacy of young students.

However, at present, the teaching of mother tongue, more specifically, mother tongue and reading literacy in primary education is carried out in somewhat difficult socio-cultural conditions, which reflects the uncertainty of social, political and ideological changes. reflects, which affects the quality of students' knowledge.

The pedagogue chooses different forms and methods of organizing native language and reading literacy lessons for the students' desire to gain knowledge in the subject of mother tongue and reading literacy, for primary school students to be interested in working in the classroom, from entertainment materials should use, develop game situations. Cognitive interest arouses the

student's interest in the mother tongue and reading literacy, and it helps to improve the quality of knowledge in the subject. The educational process means an integral system of organizing learning of the material of school subjects. The school education system based on the principles of the integrity of education and upbringing: mastering the main educational material; deepening and developing knowledge on specific issues; is focused on developing students' interest in science. Students' interest in science is especially actively developed if the forms of educational organization are used in the lessons, such as creative tasks, use of game methods of teaching. Most of the teachers rightly believe that the game is a very important activity for a student of primary school age. It is he who helps to form a new leading activity. That's why scientists, methodologists, advanced teachers always recommend introducing game teaching methods in educational processes.

Everyone knows that the beginning of a student's education at school is a difficult and responsible stage in his life. Six or seven-year-old children experience a psychological crisis related to the need to adapt to school. The child undergoes changes in leading activities: before school, children are mainly engaged in games, and when they come to school, they begin to master educational activities.

The main psychological difference between play and educational activity is that play activity is free, completely independent - the child plays when he wants, chooses the topic, tools for the game, chooses the role according to his wishes. , makes a plot, etc. Educational activities are built on the basis of voluntary efforts of the child. He is sometimes forced to do something he does not want to do, because learning activities are based on voluntary behavior skills. The transition from play to learning activities is often imposed on the child by adults and does not happen naturally.

Researches and studies conducted by many psychologists of the world show that the game does not die when preschool age ends, but not only continues to live, but even develops in its own way. It is impossible to consider a lesson in a modern school as full-fledged without the wise use of games in the educational process. Because as soon as he steps on the threshold of kindergarten, he has not yet left the game process.

Currently, special attention is paid to the development of creative activity and interest in science among schoolchildren. Various competitions, Olympiads, championships are held. This shows that the principle of the primary education student's activity in the educational process was and remains one of the main ones in didactics. This concept refers to the quality of activity characterized by a high level of motivation, a conscious need to acquire knowledge and skills, performance and compliance with social norms. Based on this, it can be said that this type of activity is rare by itself, it is the result of purposeful managerial pedagogical influences and the organization of a pedagogical environment, that is, practical pedagogical technology.

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